

DRiVE

Demand Response Integration tEchnologies:

Unlocking the demand response potential in the distribution grid

Project H2020 n° 774431

D8.2 Project Website and baseline dissemination materials

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Abstract

Information about the creation, architecture, design, implementation and maintenance of the project's website, as well as details of the plan for the social media networks of DRiVE (Twitter and LinkedIn).

Presentation of the branding materials developed, and in plan to produce, used for the communication of the project.

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Table of Contents

1	INTRODUCTION	6
2	WEBSITE	7
2.1	Design and implementation	7
2.2	Website content	7
2.2.1	Architecture	7
2.2.2	Website's components	8
2.2.2.1	News widget	8
2.2.2.2	Social networks widgets	8
2.2.2.3	Cookies	8
2.3	Webpages description	9
2.3.1	Home	9
2.3.2	About	9
2.3.3	Team	10
2.3.4	Communication	11
2.3.5	News	11
2.3.6	Contact	11
2.3.7	Private area	12
2.4	Synergies	12
2.5	Technical details	12
2.5.1	Server and domain	12
2.5.2	Maintenance	12
2.5.3	Audience scorecard	12
3	SOCIAL MEDIA	14
4	COMMUNICATION MATERIALS	16
4.1	Logo	16
4.2	Brochure	16
4.3	Poster	18
5	CONCLUSIONS	19

List of figures

Figure 1: Map of www.h2020-drive.eu	7
Figure 2: Widgets at the bottom of the home page	8
Figure 3: Home page.....	9
Figure 4: About page - Project.....	10
Figure 5: Team page	10
Figure 6: News page	11
Figure 7: Contact form.....	11
Figure 8: LinkedIn page.....	14
Figure 9: Twitter profile.....	15
Figure 10: Project's logo.....	16
Figure 11: DRIVe's brochure (external side).....	17
Figure 12: DRIVe's brochure (internal side)	17
Figure 13: DRIVe's poster	18

1 INTRODUCTION

This report provides a basic understanding of key focal development principles considered during the implementation of DRIVe's website. In addition, a description of the website's current architectural structure and initial instantiation as of May 2018 is presented. The website was designed and implemented by R2M, using the open source *WordPress* content management system. Technical specifications, graphic reproductions, and future development strategies will be presented herewith and are subject to change as the consortium sees fit and project requirements evolve.

R2M will maintain the website throughout the project lifecycle, and oversee its evolution from inception to completion. Some of the many goals to be achieved include project cross cutting through knowledge transfer, data exchange and creative dissemination activities. The website is currently composed of ten public webpages, and it is linked to two private portals reserved to the project consortium partners. The site also acts as synergistic landing page to optimise search engine rankings and create project awareness through a harmonic and robust online presence. Supportive communication channels heavily linked within the project website will align with current digital trends and technical standards. Some examples include, but are not limited to, Twitter, LinkedIn, post news, etc. Unifying semiotics and colour schemes, as well as effective linkage to sister platforms and partnering websites, will ease the browsing process in parallel to increase stakeholder engagement.

There are several purposes of the website, most notably to allow for a unified identity and a platform for interested parties to quickly gain access to key project facts, scope and objectives. In order to make the website a lively environment with an identifiable brand identity, eliciting user involvement and gathering relevant data to support the achievement of project objectives, several methodologies will be borrowed from e-marketing best practices. This expanded visibility will help to convey a holistic and accurate depiction of project goals and results while stimulating two-way communications, both internally and externally.

The aspiration of the consortium goes beyond a final solution at this moment, but instead takes the lead of further enhancements both in terms of content and technologies according to the project stakeholders evolving needs. The over-arching objective of the website, in conjunction with the interrelated social networking profiles, is to foster cooperation among DRIVe consortium members, special interest groups, relevant research and/or commercial projects, and industrial initiatives such as events, workshops and newsfeeds.

This report also provides a basic understanding of key focal development principles considered during the implementation of the project's public communication materials. A description of the materials created until this date, and the planned materials for the future, is presented.

The communication materials represent the visual identity of DRIVe, being an invaluable tool to help disseminate the project across the interested stakeholders but also within academia and the general public. The initial materials are oriented to the general public, because as of now our main objective is to introduce the project to as many people as possible. These materials also can be used to reach specific stakeholders in industries and academia, because they contain technical specifications, graphic reproductions, and future development strategies of the project. Through the project's lifecycle it will be possible to create additional and more detailed communication materials targeted to different specific stakeholders.

2 Website

The URL is www.h2020-drive.es, launched in month 6 of the project by R2M. The website contains relevant information about the project, partners, activities and developments of DRIVe. It is also a platform to release all public communication and dissemination materials.

The website is the face of the project and is constantly updated.

2.1 DESIGN AND IMPLEMENTATION

DRIVe’s website clearly describes the project specifications from a high-level perspective with a heavy use of info-graphics. Subsequently, for interested parties, a clear path is set forth towards finding more technical and non-technical details as well as entry points for collaborations. The goal is for both visitors and administrators to have an interactive central landing page that can provide essential functionalities while being both informative and user-friendly.

The appearance of the website reflects the public image and identity of the project through a clean and simple functional design with key calls to action presented across several touch points. The site was officially launched on May 28th, 2018. Essentially, an over-simplification of technical terms will occur and be presented in a user-friendly format so as to effectively teach visitors what the project is all about, why they should care, and how they can get involved.

2.2 WEBSITE CONTENT

For a briefing of the evolving architectural and graphical user interface structure, in Figure 1 there is a hierarchical process map which was used to develop the overall navigation process while keeping user experience at the forefront of all decisions.

2.2.1 Architecture

The structure of the website is a key determining factor to its overall success. Grounded in user-centricity, surfers must not be confused as to where to find the desired information and they must be able to perform any call to action such as sharing or downloading documents within one or two clicks at the most. These actions should take less than 15 seconds at most so as to avoid a high drop off rate. Figure 1 outlines the initial vision for the site in a graphical process map to assist in high-level decisions and usability optimisation.

Figure 1: Map of www.h2020-drive.eu

2.2.2 Website's components

There are several key widgets that will strategically be placed throughout the website: share in social media, LinkedIn, Twitter, etc. The following subsections present some of the social network platforms we plan to use in the next few months. The intention is to create a comprehensive social media profile across several unified platforms and, subsequently, provide easy access points in many different locations while also sprinkling the links on most project public communications. These social media profiles will all share a common identifying colour scheme, informative keyword utilization, and other branding related KPIs such as tone of voice, calls to action, etc.

2.2.2.1 News widget

At the bottom right of the homepage has been inserted a widget displaying the latest news of the website.

2.2.2.2 Social networks widgets

At the bottom of the homepage, the Twitter icon and LinkedIn icon (both of the social media accounts the project has) are displayed, taking the user to those accounts with one click.

Figure 2: Widgets at the bottom of the home page

2.2.2.3 Cookies

When entering the website for the first time, a note of cookies is displayed. Upon accepting in a web browser, the note is no longer displayed for subsequent access to the website. The cookies text reads:

“This site uses cookies - small text files that are placed on your machine to help the site provide a better user experience. In general, cookies are used to retain user preferences, store information for things like shopping carts, and provide anonymised tracking data to third party applications like Google Analytics. As a rule, cookies will make your browsing experience better. However, you may prefer to disable cookies on this site and on others. The most effective way to do this is to disable cookies in your browser.”

2.3 WEBPAGES DESCRIPTION

2.3.1 Home

The home webpage is the website's landing page, and it is the destination if users click on the logo located on any of the webpages.

The home page is presented with a video (displaying representative images of the DRiVE solution), just below the header, with catching images and key messages, and a short introduction of the justification of the project. The latest news is presented on the bottom left side, and on the right side the latest tweets. Finally, Twitter and LinkedIn icons are inserted at the centre of the bottom banner to follow and visit DRiVE's accounts.

Figure 3: Home page

2.3.2 About

This section is divided into two webpages: “Project” which describes the objectives of DRiVE and a summary of its developments, and “Demo sites” which introduces the 5 pilots of the project (Blaenau Gwent District, DEVO District, Giessenwind wind farm, ADO Stadium and COMSA head office).

ABOUT DRiVe

To break out of the current status quo, DRiVe will develop and validate a fully-integrated ICT infrastructure consisting of interoperable DR-enabling Energy Management solutions for residential and tertiary buildings and platform for effective and secure management of flexibility at the level of the distribution grid.

The DRiVe undermining process will consist of 3 phases:

1. Unlock DR potential of buildings
2. Enable effective and secure decentralised management of the grid
3. Make a synergistic use of validation activities to boost DRiVe's development

Figure 4: About page - Project

2.3.3 Team

In this section of the website, there is a list of the project partners with a brief summary of their work, along with live hyperlinks leading to the respective partner's profile. This initiative will consolidate the assumption of transparency, which is an important aspect to publicly funded research.

DRIVE CONSORTIUM

The DRiVe Consortium represents a multi-disciplinary group composed of 8 partners representing 7 EU countries, which stands for an ideal platform to carry out the work proposed. The different tasks planned in this project would not be feasible without the contribution of each of the partners, which have been specifically selected for the execution of the tasks, according to the needs of DRiVe.

Figure 5: Team page

2.3.4 Communication

This webpage is not available yet. It will be dedicated to the dissemination of all the content created to promote the project: “Media” (multimedia gallery with videos, pictures, presentations, etc.) and “Publications” (contributions on conferences, papers, public events, etc.).

2.3.5 News

Press releases related to DRIVe core topic areas, both self-generated and authored by parties external to the consortium, will play a large part in the overall dissemination strategy and the overall success metrics of the project dissemination and exploitation activities.

Kick-off Meeting

admin - December 15, 2017 - Uncategorized

DRIVe's Kick-off Meeting was held in Saclay, France the days 11th and 12th December, 2017. The event was organized by CEA in their quality of Project Coordinator. It was a great opportunity to introduce each partner and their capabilities, as well as explaining their contributions to DRIVe. [\(more...\)](#)

[CONTINUE READING >](#)

Figure 6: News page

2.3.6 Contact

A high level of stakeholder engagement will be critical, and the systematic operational processes and platforms will be standardized to assist in promotional efforts. To further assist stakeholder interaction, a contact form is provided in this webpage.

CONTACT US

Your Name (required)

Your Email (required)

Subject

Your Message

Figure 7: Contact form

2.3.7 Private area

This is the entry point to the project's repository, ownCloud¹, and to the project management system, both platforms managed by R2M. These are private portals where members of the consortium can access and interact with all the work that is being done in the project.

2.4 SYNERGIES

Cross-platform streamlining helps to prove project identity, and to engage new stakeholder groups loyal to the platform in question. In other words, the project hopes to achieve a high level of dissemination, which cannot be achieved through simply using a website and nothing else. Consequently, researchers must maintain a deep understanding of the rapidly changing technologies because these tools can bring about a globalized efficiency expansion by connecting stakeholders and being able to reach the desired audiences.

With this in mind, a Twitter account and a LinkedIn profile have been created for DRiVE, both accounts managed by R2M.

2.5 TECHNICAL DETAILS

The infrastructure supporting the project dedicated website are explained here, along with a brief introduction to the social media networking tools that have been considered.

2.5.1 Server and domain

The official registration of the domain name used for the project's public website is <https://www.h2020-drive.eu/>. The domain name will be registered under the .eu domain for at least one year after the contractual end of the project completion. R2M has committed to keep the website alive and active for at least that period of time. The web server is hosted using *WordPress* 4.9. We used the ARUBA hosting (hosting.aruba.it) using the Hosting Easy Linux plan. The plan includes Hosting with Linux operating system, MySQL server 5.5 as database, backup space for MySQL data, web space backup, unlimited emails, 10 GigaMails, IMAP emails, business emails and statistics. The web server is Apache, which includes PHP Version 5.5.17.

2.5.2 Maintenance

As administrators of the site, R2M is directly responsible for leading the calls for contributions, graphic design, technical development and the overall online profile management. R2M will also continue to perform regular content updates ensuring that all press releases, journal publications, deliverables, etc., are posted in a timely manner. R2M is responsible for and has the sole administrative rights to make modifications to the website's structural composition, and will elicit validation when necessary. The website will ultimately be designed to satisfy the project needs and aspirations while abiding to the communication strategy according to "EU project Websites – Best Practice Guidelines (March 2010)"².

2.5.3 Audience scorecard

A strong foundation in search engine optimisation will drive keyword-rich social signals by intertwining the key project objectives with the desired stakeholder participation. The need for sufficient analytic

¹ For more information see deliverable 1.2.

² http://www.eurosfair.prdd.fr/7pc/documents/1271333123_project_website_guidelines_en.pdf accessed on May 3rd 2018.

responsiveness is the quintessential determining factor to allow for efficient and effective communications, and to help improve organic search rankings. The utility served by registering with Google Analytics³ facility will allow for rich reports to be generated and analysed accordingly, giving a very clear picture of information such as:

- Number of users visiting the site;
- What links and pages are more popular than others;
- What websites the users are coming from;
- Where the visitors are coming from geographically.

It is imperative that we identify the project communication content that best reaches the targeted audiences, and concurrently be able to monitor communication campaigns.

Google Analytics has been embedded into DRiVE's website in order to analyse the visitation patterns, browser demographics, and other important insights required for growth to occur while keeping user-centricity at the forefront of adaptations.

³ <http://www.google.com/analytics/>

3 Social Media

Social media allows DRIVe to reach an extremely wide — but also targeted — audience, maximising the impact and successful exploitation of the research results. The idea is to use these platforms to communicate the project to multiple audiences and to disseminate project results to stakeholders.

Following the guidelines in the document “Social media guide for EU funded R&I projects”⁴, we performed a SWOT and a PEST analysis, and we came to the conclusion that the best social media networks for DRIVe are Twitter and LinkedIn. R2M will manage these accounts.

In Twitter we will communicate the project in a general way, to a general audience, but we will also use it to interact with other research projects in order to create a DR-cluster, and in that way, share relevant information.

In LinkedIn we will try to reach stakeholders, especially in the industry, with whom we can disseminate the project and create relationships to exploit DRIVe’s results.

In May 28th 2018 these social media accounts for DRIVe were launched:

LinkedIn: A company page was created in order to further disseminate the project among professionals related to smart grids and to create debates and share useful information.

Figure 8: LinkedIn page

⁴ http://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/h2020/other/grants_manual/amga/soc-med-guide_en.pdf accessed on May 3rd 2018.

Twitter: An account in this social media is useful to spread the project to a wider audience, as well as sharing the developments and resources of DRiVE along the course of the project's life.

Figure 9: Twitter profile

Links to these profiles have been displayed in the website.

4 Communication materials

These materials are relevant to introduce DRIVe to the widest audience possible. They are the visual identity of the project and, besides being displayed in our website, will be printed, being a tool to present the project to everyone who may be interested.

4.1 LOGO

The logo was the first development in the visual identity set. It captures the essence of the project with the slogan “unlocking DR potential”, represented by the key hole being opened by the plug.

Figure 10: Project's logo

4.2 BROCHURE

A first introductory brochure of DRIVe has been developed. It is in size A4 to facilitate its view and its printing. The idea is that all partners can use the brochure as a resource to easily disseminate the project in different scenarios.

Figure 11: DRIVE's brochure (external side)

Figure 12: DRIVE's brochure (internal side)

4.3 POSTER

DRivE also has a size A0 poster. The objective of the poster is to briefly explain the project, and can be used in some public events (such as conferences) and also displayed in the offices of the partners.

DRIVE

DEMO SITES

DRivE will demonstrate the effectiveness of the proposed flexibility management platform through a wide set of validation activities involving 5 pilot sites and globally covering all services within the DR value chain.

- Bancku District (demo) "The smart city" in the United Kingdom
- DEVO District in the Netherlands
- Overseasland wind farm in the Netherlands
- GARS FANS STADIUM
- ADVO Stadium in the Netherlands
- CONRAD Hotel in Spain

WHAT IS DRIVE

DRivE links together cutting-edge science in artificial intelligence, forecasting and cyber security with emerging innovative SMEs making first market penetration in EU DR markets. In doing so, near market solutions are strengthened with innovative functionalities that support a vision of an "Internet of energy" and "collaborative energy network." DRivE uses artificial intelligence to bring decentralized management and DR services to prosumers, grid stakeholders and distribution system operators.

DRivE'S OBJECTIVES

- Unlock DR potential in residential and tertiary buildings through low cost solutions that are universally interoperable, integrating innovative load prediction and optimization algorithms
- Optimize distribution grid flexibility through an integrated Multi-agent based Demand Response ICT platform for aggregators integrating last advances in distributed real-time control architecture, artificial intelligence and communications
- Demonstration of secure communication through the design and development of cyber-security components for Smart Grids
- Engage and stimulate customers to participate in DR programs through a consumer portal

WHY DRIVE

It is widely recognised that increasing flexibility is key for the reliable operation of future power systems with very high penetration levels of Variable Renewable Energy Sources (VRES). Flexibility is the ability of a power system to maintain continuous service in the face of rapid and large swings in supply or demand. The most significant source of flexibility in a future scenario with high penetration of VRES is Demand Response (DR). The new challenge is to unlock the very high potential of DR in the distribution grid where the main sources of flexibility are the residential and tertiary buildings representing 70% of the total DR potential. DRivE will unlock the Demand Response potential of residential and tertiary buildings in the distribution grid through a comprehensive platform the seamlessly existing assets and buildings to achieve optimal operations in the next generation Smart Grids, paving the way to a fully deployed DR market in the distribution network.

DRivE'S PROJECT PLAN

To break out of the current status quo, DRivE will develop and validate a fully-integrated ICT infrastructure consisting of interoperable DR-enabling and Energy Management solutions for residential and tertiary buildings and platform for an effective and secure management of energy flexibility at the level of the distribution grid. The DRivE underpinning process will consist of 3 phases:

1. Unlock DR potential of buildings
2. Enable effective and secure decentralized management of the grid
3. Make a synergistic use of validation activities to boost DRivE development

PROJECT FACTS

Title: Demand Response Integration Technologies
 Acronym: DRivE
 Type of action: Research and Innovation Action
 Budget: € 3,555,250,75
 Duration: From December 2017 until November 2020 (36 months)

Partners: list, AIRBUS, CH2M HILL, Energy Labs, COMSA, FGM SOLUTION, Enervit, Typhoon HX, SCHOTT

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement n° 774431

Figure 13: DRivE's poster

5 Conclusions

DRIVE's website is an integral element of the project dissemination strategy and will simultaneously ensure project visibility and facilitate the diffusion of exploitable results. The website provides a basic set of information about the project and will be regularly updated with scientific results, findings and achievements.

Popularity and promotion of the site will be increased through active link-building initiatives to capitalize on the existing websites and social networking platforms of project partners. Relevant EU projects, institutions and thought-leaders within the stakeholder group(s) will become the primary targets after using appropriate methods to build the communicative reach.

The information contained on the project website is likely to be valuable even after the project has finished. Therefore, R2M aims at ensuring that the website will continue to exist after the project implementation period has finished.

DRIVE's website will be a dynamic, vibrant piece of infrastructure that is continuously updated as the needs of the project change, content is generated by all work packages and improved software tools become available.

All changes to the website will be driven by the needs of the project as they arise throughout its lifetime and in consultation with the appropriate project partners.

On the other hand, the public communication materials are an integral element of the project's communication and dissemination strategy, which will simultaneously ensure visibility of DRIVE and facilitate the diffusion of its exploitable results. These materials provide a basic set of information about the project and will be regularly updated with scientific results, findings and achievements.